

cultivar with excellent palatability and resistance to bacterial blight and blast.

NAU2159 was developed from a cross between Nanjing 11, a popular local variety, in Jiangsu Province, and IR29, a donor of disease resistance and waxy endperm.

In 4 yr demonstration (1985-88) along

the lower and middle reaches of the Yangtze River Valley, yields were 7-9 t/ha, 7.5 t/ha average. NAU2159 matures early (duration 130-135 d) and is adapted to the areas flanked by 29-34°N latitude, where a traditional rice - wheat cropping system prevails. Its

better performance results from the unique combination of traits inherited from both parents (see table).

It is acceptable to farmers in Henan, Anhui, Jiangsu, Jiangxi, and Guizhao Provinces, with more than 50,000 ha planted. □

Performance of some promising rice cultivars for tidal marshy swamps of Andamans

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We screened 330 cultivars during 1988 to identify a suitable rice variety for the low-lying marshy areas along the tidal creeks of Andamans. Cultures included

advanced bulk populations, elite lines, and F₁ anther culture derivatives from IRRI.

Seedlings (21-d-old) were transplanted in a field with normal soil and in a screening plot close to the sea (soil EC 6.5 dS/m and pH 4.2). The screening plot was allowed to be fully inundated by 50-60 cm seawater 7 d after transplanting. That water was maintained through the cropping period by bunding the experimental plot.

Rainfall totaled 2,930 mm during 1988 cropping season. EC varied from 2 to

6.5 dS/m and pH, from 3.9 to 4.6. In the screening plot, all but 18 advanced bulk populations from IRRI, 6 elite lines from India, and the local check died. The surviving 25 lines are of long duration and short-statured (see table).

Local variety C-14-8, culture 88-038, and culture 88-121 are found to be promising. □

Agronomic traits related to tolerance for salinity of some promising rice cultures in the marshy swamps of Andamans.^a

Designation	Source	Phenotypic index (0-9)	Days to 50% flowering ^b	Plant height (cm)		Panicle-bearing tillers (no.)		Panicle length (cm)		Seed yield/plant (g)	
				(a)	(r)	(a)	(r)	(a)	(r)	(a)	(r)
88-027	IRRI	6	155	51.0	47.4	6.0	83.3	12.6	54.3	6.0	27.8
88-048	IRRI	9	na	55.5	58.2	3.4	68.0	16.5	68.5	6.8	52.3
88-092	IRRI	5	153	41.8	45.5	7.0	74.5	18.3	72.7	7.0	23.3
88-127	IRRI	3	153	49.0	54.8	6.0	76.9	17.4	83.3	8.4	44.9
88-091	IRRI	4	130	51.6	57.2	4.3	69.4	18.6	78.8	11.2	82.4
88-121	IRRI	4	148	58.8	64.1	5.0	62.5	19.5	95.6	14.0	35.0
88-106	IRRI	4	150	61.4	67.3	3.4	77.3	19.6	86.7	3.4	38.6
88-104	IRRI	7	135	62.2	70.7	3.4	77.3	21.3	99.1	7.5	56.8
88-097	IRRI	7	na	51.4	60.7	3.8	76.0	12.6	64.3	7.6	25.3
88-088	IRRI	7	160	48.0	51.7	3.3	37.5	14.3	74.5	6.9	19.6
88-038	IRRI	5	140	59.5	73.5	5.0	89.3	15.1	83.9	15.0	53.6
88-063	IRRI	4	155	42.3	54.4	4.5	88.9	18.3	80.3	4.0	49.4
88-006	IRRI	5	121	44.7	62.1	3.0	50.0	9.9	57.6	3.0	25.0
88-126	IRRI	5	145	72.0	81.6	4.0	64.5	16.2	70.7	4.4	29.5
88-012	IRRI	6	na	48.9	53.6	4.5	62.5	17.5	81.4	9.0	57.0
88-080	IRRI	6	na	46.3	52.4	4.0	71.4	13.7	59.6	4.0	39.6
88-032	IRRI	3	147	79.0	74.8	6.0	51.7	18.8	88.3	8.4	18.1
88-071	IRRI	9	120	52.5	56.0	3.2	84.2	16.2	69.2	3.2	28.1
SR26-B	India	3	129	95.6	93.3	3.0	83.3	11.6	56.9	3.0	38.0
CO 43	India	5	137	55.8	66.1	4.0	76.9	14.8	67.9	4.0	29.6
CST100-1	India	5	140	52.6	87.1	3.8	95.0	15.4	92.2	5.7	47.5
CSR3	India	5	153	51.8	68.6	2.2	47.8	15.3	86.0	4.0	43.5
316	India	5	138	59.8	68.7	3.5	83.3	14.3	69.8	2.7	29.3
F35	India	5	129	58.5	68.3	5.0	84.0	12.6	68.9	4.2	84.0
C-14-8	India	5	155	142.4	87.4	5.4	58.6	20.6	86.9	11.6	50.4

^a(a) = actual value under saline condition.

(r) = relative value = $\frac{\text{performance under saline condition}}{\text{performance under normal condition}} \times 100$

^bna = not available.

Zhongyu 87-1, promising line developed through shuttle breeding

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Zhongyu 87-1—a high-yielding, medium-duration, multiple-resistance, and wide-adaptability variety developed from the cross Kwangluai 4/IR64 through the IRRI-CNIRRI Shuttle Breeding project—can be grown in middle season or late season. It is resistant to blast and whitebacked planthopper and moderately resistant to bacterial blight and brown planthopper.

In a late season 1988 hybrid rice demonstration test in Zhejiang Province, it yielded higher than Shanyou 6 (hybrid check) in five of six sites (Table 1). In farmers' fields in Zhejiang, it averaged 7.5 t/ha, 7.26% higher than Shanyou 6. In preliminary regional adaptability tests in Hubei Province in middle season 1988, its yield was significantly higher than that of check variety Quichao 2 in three locations (Table 2).

Zhongyu 87-1 has medium height (90-100 cm), compact plant type, and